

Complexes of Metal Ions with Phosphorus or Arsenic containing Ligands: Part IV. Complexes of Zinc (II) Halides with 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine

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Complexes of Zinc (II) halides have been prepared with 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine which are of the general formula $Zn(\text{diphos})X_2$ where X is Cl, Br or I. On the basis of conductance data of their solutions in nitrobenzene and infrared spectra, these have been assigned chelate structures with tetrahedral stereochemistry.

Wide interest has been shown in the ligating property of phosphorus compounds. The formation of Zinc (II) halide complexes with triethylphosphine have been reported in literature^{1,2}. Complexes of some bidentate ligands such as 1,2-ethylenebis(diethyl)phosphine have also been prepared and their properties investigated^{3,4}.

In the present project, the study of complexing ability of ditertiaryphosphines and arsines such as 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine/arsine and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine/arsine have been undertaken. In a previous communication⁵ the complexes of Mercury (II) halides with 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine have been reported, in which the interesting feature of the bidentate and monodentate (bridging) nature of these ligands has been illustrated⁵. In the present communication, the complexes of Zinc (II) halides (chloride, bromide and iodide) with 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine (EDP) and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine (BDP) are reported.

The alcoholic solutions of Zinc (II) halide and the ditertiary phosphine (EDP or BDP) on mixing, yield white crystalline air stable solids. The analytical results of these complexes lead to the assignment of a general formula $Zn(\text{Diphos})X_2$. Physical properties and analytical results are given in Table I.

The complexes are thermally stable which is indicated by their high melting points. The conductance of millimolar solutions of the complexes has been measured in nitrobenzene which indicates that these exist as non-electrolytes. An analogous complex of Zinc(II)

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1. M. J. Schmelz, M. A. G. Hill, and C. Curran, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 1273.
2. W. E. Hatfield and J. T. Yokes, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 475.
3. G. E. Coates and D. Ridley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 166.
4. C. E. Wymore and J. C. Bailer, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **14**, 42.
5. S. S. Sandhu, and M. P. Gupta, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.* (in press).

TABLE I

Name of complex	Melting point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Molar conductance in nitrobenzene $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Phosphorus %		Halogen %		Zinc %	
			Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found
1. Dichloro 1,2-ethylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	290	1.3	11.58	11.65	13.29	13.04	12.22	11.72
2. Dibromo 1,2-ethylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	284-85	1.1	9.93	10.17	25.67	25.40	10.48	10.20
3. Di-iodo 1,2-ethylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	Above 290	1.3	8.63	8.34	35.37	34.87	9.10	8.71
4. Dichloro 1,4-butylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	250-52	1.7	11.01	10.86	12.62	12.10	11.62	11.01
5. Dibromo 1,4-butylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	240-43	1.1	9.50	9.62	24.57	24.42	10.05	9.58
6. Di-iodo 1,4-butylene-bisdiphenylphosphine Zinc (II)	240-41	1.6	8.32	7.92	34.09	33.40	8.72	8.18

bromide with 1,2-ethylenebisdiethylphosphine has also been reported to be a non-electrolyte in nitrobenzene⁴. Molecular weight of these complexes could not be determined due to insufficient solubility in various solvents.

Zinc (II) is a d^{10} ion which usually adopts a coordination number four with tetrahedral stereochemistry, though coordination number five, six and eight are also known for it^{6,7,8}. The infrared spectra of these complexes indicate the coordination of phosphorus to the metal ion, since the $\text{P-C}_{(\text{aromatic})}$ stretching frequency at 1100 cm^{-1} in the free ligands shifts to a higher value by $10-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Similar observations have been reported by other workers also⁹.

On the basis of these data and keeping in view the structure assigned to analogous complexes of Zinc (II) halides with *o*-phenylenebisdimethylarsine¹⁰ and 1,2-ethylene bisdiethylphosphine⁴, these complexes may be assigned four coordinate chelate structure.

6. K. A. Frazer and H. M. Harding, *Acta. Cryst.*, 1967, 22, 75.
7. S. Chose, *Acta. Cryst.*, 1964, 17, 105.
8. D. P. Graddon and D. G. Weeden, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 247.
9. C. B. Deacon and J. H. S. Green, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1965, 1031.
10. J. Lewis, R. S. Nyholm and D. G. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2177.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of ditertiaryphosphines. EDP was prepared by the method reported in literature¹¹. BDP was prepared by a similar method using 1,4-butylenedibromide in place of ethylenedichloride.

Preparation of complexes : The complexes were prepared by mixing alcoholic solutions of Zinc (II) halide and the ditertiary phosphine in molar ratio 1.5 to 1 with constant shaking. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under vacuum.

Elemental analysis : Halogen was estimated by Volhardi's method after fusing a known weight of the complex with Sodium hydroxide in a sealed tube. Phosphorus was estimated by fusing a known weight of the complex with fusion mixture and then precipitating phosphorus as ammonium phosphomolybdate¹². Zinc was determined as $Zn(NH_4)PO_4$ after decomposition of the complex¹².

Molar conductance : Conductance of milimolar solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene was measured using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge type CLOI/OI.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer (Model 337) spectrophotometer.

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11. J. Chatt and F. A. Hart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1378.
12. A. I. Vogel, "A text book of quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., 1962, pp. 402, 533.